

Appendix A Literature review

We started with an initial pool of 271 papers obtained from forward snowballing on the review papers by [1] and [2]. We then filtered this set by selecting papers with the keywords “dashboard”, “peer”, “reference”, or “social” in their titles or abstracts, reducing the list to 123 papers. Next, we refined the selection by reviewing the abstracts to focus on studies that (1) present a LAD solution, (2) are student-oriented, and (3) incorporate a social comparison feature, narrowing the scope to 33 relevant papers. We further expanded this set by including relevant papers reviewed by [1] (specifically LADs with a social feedback component) and [2] (specifically student-facing LADs that provide feedback on learning progress), bringing the total to 54 papers. To ensure alignment with our study’s focus, we applied additional criteria by thoroughly reading each paper, retaining only those that (1) target higher education, (2) provide feedback on students’ study progress, activity, or performance, (3) utilize course activity data from Learning Management System (LMS), Virtual Learning Environment (VLE), or tool data, (4) involve explicit student participation in the LAD evaluation, and (5) explicitly report peer comparison features. The final set of 23 papers is summarized in Table 1, offering a comparative view across multiple dimensions.

Table 1: Related work. Abbreviations: PC, peer comparison; BG, background; A, activity; P, performance; SP, study progress; BL, blended learning; OL, online learning; Nat. Sci., Natural Sciences; Educ., Education; Med., Medicine; Bus., Business; CME, Conceptual Modeling Education; Engr., Engineering; +, Positive; -, Negative.

Ref.	Domain	Faculty	Setting	Evaluation method	PC researched?	BG researched?	Data sources for LAD	Feedback Topic
[3]	Multi	Multi	BL	Surveys; interviews	Mixed	No	Formative and summative assessment grades; LMS data	A; P; SP
[4]	/	/	BL	Controlled experiment; surveys; interviews	+	No	LMS data	A; P; SP
[5]	Multi	Multi	OL	Questionnaire; log data analysis	+	No	LMS data	A; SP
[6]	STEM	CS	BL	Log data analysis; survey	+	No	Course resources access	A; P; SP
[7]	Nat.Sci.	Nat.Sci.	OL	Questionnaire	+	No	LMS data	A
[8]	Multi	Multi	OL	Questionnaire; log data analysis	+	No	LMS data	A
[9]	STEM	STEM	OL; BL	Controlled experiment; questionnaire	+	No	Formative assessment grades	P
[10]	Multi	Educ.	BL	Questionnaire	Mixed	No	LMS data	A; P; SP
[11]	Med.	Med.	OL	Questionnaire	+	No	VLE data	A; P; SP
[12]	Multi	Multi	In-class	Controlled experiment; interviews; questionnaire	-	No	LMS data	A; P; SP
[13]	/	/	BL	Controlled experiment; questionnaires	+	No	LMS & connected tools data	A; P
[14]	STEM	CS	BL	Questionnaire; interviews; log data analysis	Mixed	No	Course resources access	A; P; SP
[15]	STEM	CS	BL; OL	Surveys; interviews; controlled experiment	+	No	LMS data	A; P; SP
[16]	STEM	Bus.	Flipped class-room	Focus groups; interviews; survey	Mixed	No	LMS & programming & video streaming tools data	A; P
[17]	STEM	/	OL	Controlled experiment; surveys; interviews	Mixed	No	LMS data	SP; P
[18]	STEM	Engr.	In-class	Interviews and user observations; questionnaires (with open ended questions)	+	No	Time spent on tools, websites and IDE	A
[19]	STEM	Engr.	OL	Questionnaires; log data analysis	+	No	e-textbook & LMS data	A
[20]	STEM	CS	BL	Survey; controlled experiment; log data analysis	+	Yes	Course resources access	A; P; SP
[21]	Multi	Multi	MOOC	Controlled experiment	+	Yes	LMS data	A
[22]	STEM	CS	BL	Controlled experiment; log data analysis; self-reports from students	+	Yes	Course resources access	A; P; SP
[23]	Bus.	Bus.	OL	Interviews	Mixed	Yes	VLE data; assignments grades	A; P; SP
[24]	Multi	Multi	BL	Interviews; questionnaire; focus groups; log data analysis	+	Yes	VLE data	A; P; SP
[25]	STEM	CS	OL; BL	Controlled experiment; log data analysis	+	Yes	LMS data	A
Our study	CME	Bus.	BL	Log data analysis	?	Yes	Modeling tool & LMS data; formative grades; offline attendance	A; P; SP

Appendix B Historical performance

Table 2: Historical performance based on the final grade (including retakes). Statistical significance is test using Mann–Whitney U test.

Academic year	MInfM avg. grade	MBISE avg. grade	Significantly different?
AY 2017-2018	12.1	13.3	No
AY 2018-2019	11.3	13.7	Yes
AY 2019-2020	11.8	14.0	Yes
AY 2020-2021	11.7	13.1	Yes
AY 2021-2022	10.7	12.1	Yes
AY 2022-2023	9.9	12.5	Yes

Appendix C Visualizations questionnaire

Fig. 1: Exercise sessions

Fig. 2: Home Assignments

Fig. 3: Modeling activity

Fig. 4: Number of online exercise sessions

Fig. 5: Score on online exercise sessions

Fig. 6: Number of online quizzes

Fig. 7: Score on online quizzes

Fig. 8: Practice test score

Fig. 9: Ranking of visualizations

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